

Investigating Differences in Achievement Motivation Between Participants in Team Sports and Individual Sports

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present study to Investigating Differences in Achievement Motivation Between Participants in Team Sports and Individual Sports in Punjabi University, Patiala. The age of subjects was ranging from 18 to 24 years. The criterion measure chosen was analysed by descriptive analysis and one sample t- test to compare the level between the team games players and individual players. The level of significance chosen to test the hypothesis was 0.05, p, 0.05. The collected data was analysed and one sample t- test to compare depression level among different games.

The obtain data statistically represent the mean of sports achievement motivation with regard to team games is 21.44 and standard deviation is 3.74 where as in case of individual game, the mean value is 17.32 and standard deviation is 3.30. The study also revealed that there were no significant different found between team game player and individual players. The results shows that sports achievement motivation level of team game players is higher than that of individual players.

KEYWORDS: Sports Achievement Motivation, Team Sports vs Individual Sports, Sports Psychology, Athlete Motivation, Comparative Study, Performance Motivation, Psychological Factors in Sports, Achievement Behaviour

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INTRODUCTION

Today, sport and exercise psychologists have begun to research and provide information in the ways that psychological well-being and vigorous physical activity are related. This idea of psychophysiology, used in monitoring brain activity during exercise has combined with our study. Also, sport psychologists are often to put exercise to be a therapeutic addition to healthy mental adjustment and behaviour.

Motive is one of the most important concepts explored by Physiology. Motives underlie the human and animal behaviours. Motives may be kind of known and comprehensible today or of unknown and incomprehensible clearly for now.

According to Arslanogluna (2005) motive is one of the factors prompting a person to take an action or to choose one of the many action options and perform relative continuous (1,2).

Motivation is one of the most popular research topics in sport psychology, and the reason for this may be that it has been continually reported as an important factor in affecting people's well-being and performance in sport (Roberts et

al.2007). A contemporary approach to the study of motivation is to consider it as a cognitive process (Roberts et al., 2002). More specifically, Roberts and colleagues (2007) argue that to understand motivation, it is important to examine the processes that energize, direct, and regulate achievement behaviour. To date, sport motivation research is strongly positioned within a social-cognitive framework, according to which, individuals cognitively process and develop their views about achievement in relation to social contexts and influences (Noumanis& Biddle, 1999).

Achievement Motivation Theory tries to explain why people attend an event, why they put so much effort to achieve an extremely difficult objective and why they maintain it for so long. It is generally considered that the competitiveness or rivalry existing in the sport evolved out of achievement motivation. The focal point of achievement need for some people is that to achieve high level satisfaction rather than to success in the event based on achievement. However, the point which must be taken into consideration is that the perception of achievement will vary from person to person. In other words, each individual is obliged to determine his/her achievement behaviour. But if the performance-based result

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identified with individual's inability or low effort, this also is considered as failure. Therefore, a situation considered to be success by one might be considered as a failure for another (3,4).

Motivation is the basic drive for all of our actions. Motivation refers to the dynamics of our behaviour, which involves our needs, desires, and ambitions in life. Achievement motivation is based on reaching success and achieving all of our aspirations in life. Achievement goals can affect the way a person performs a task and represent a desire to show competence (Harackiewicz et al., 1997).

Achievement motivation cannot be described as something that occurs during competition but mostly as a trait having permanent character, ' - being formed during the preceding weeks, months and years. Therefore, it is obvious that coaches may look for athletes who have had this characteristic at a high level from the very beginning and therefore do not need much psychological intervention. The lack of psychological knowledge by coaches in the area of motivation' is one of the main reasons for mistakes made in the talent identification process. It often causes disappointment of those players who are not predestined to practice high-professional by the basics of their personality - these players who do not possess high level of achievement motivation and they do not reach the highest levels of the game despite good results at a young age.

In general, self-confidence tends to be highest when you believe in your ability and feel that you have properly prepared for a competition. Worry and confidence are at opposite ends of the spectrum -- when confidence is strong, it tends to crowd worry out of the mind.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM-

“INVESTIGATING DIFFERENCES IN ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION BETWEEN PARTICIPANTS IN TEAM SPORTS AND INDIVIDUAL SPORTS.”

Objective of the study

1. To study the achievement motivation level of team games and individual game players.
2. To compare relationship of achievement motivation among different games.

Hypothesis

1. It is hypothesized that there is no relationship in achievement motivation among all the age groups of different games.

2. There may be the relationship between the achievement motivation of all the age groups of different games.

Limitation

1. The study is limited to the age of 18 to 24 years.
2. The study is limited to national level players of different games.
3. The players is limited to Punjabi university, Patiala.

Delimitation

1. The study is delimited to national level players.
2. In this study the players above the age to 24 and below 18 were not included.
3. The players is delimited to Punjabi university, Patiala.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

To achieve these purpose 52 male players (26 from team game, 26 from individual game) of two different groups was selected. These players were taken from team game and individual game. The subjects were randomly selected from different games at Punjabi university, Patiala and polo ground, Patiala.

The age ranged between 19-24 years. The variable selected for the present study was Sports Achievement Motivation. The study was carried out on questionnaire based on different game players. The questionnaire of achievement motivation (ACT) from V.P. Bhargava (1994) is used for this study.

Administration time:

In general, ACMT questionnaire requires to complete in 15 to 20 minutes. each questionnaire is distributed to single player. The instruction of given questionnaire is provided to each player, so that they can fill the questionnaire at given time.

Scoring:

The scoring of the filled questionnaires was done according to the instructions mentioned in the test manual for the purpose. One score was awarded to each write answer and zero to the wrong answer as mentioned in the scoring key. To obtain total score for the complete test all the scores for different items were recorded in the specified space provided in the questionnaire of the scale.

Interpretation of score:

As once the score is calculated, the result is administering the achievement motivation test (ACMT) norms. These norms are classified as follow

ACMT	Score
Category	Boys
High	23 and above
Above average	19-22
Average	17-18
Below average	15-16
Low	11-14

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Interpretation of above table shows that:

Low Category - typifies subjects' performance lower than ordinary once.

Below Average- refers subject category performance is simpler than routine performance.

Average- refers to average performance nothing worth mentioning

Above average- refers performance superior than average one. Casual an appreciation is often done.

High- refers to outstanding performances worth appreciable and mentioning.

Statistical computations:

For the adequate interpretation of the data the following statistical tests were applied.

Mean (X):

It is calculated to measure the central tendency of parameter which is the typical value in the distribution of the particular parameter. All the individual values of the variable is added and then the sum is divided by the total number of the individuals.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$$

Standard deviation (S.D.)- it is the measure of the variation and is universally used to show the scatter of individual measurement in a given distribution. By definition, it is the

square root of the average of the scattered deviation of the measurement from their mean. It is calculated as follow
The formula for the sample standard deviation is

Standard Deviation Formula = $\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N - 1}}$

Where,

x = Values given

\bar{x} = Mean

n = Total number of values.

Test of Significance-

In order to compare the performance for different tests, of different games group, T-test has been applied.

$$t = \frac{(X_1 - X_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{(S_1)^2}{n_1} + \frac{(S_2)^2}{n_2}}}$$

Where,

X_1 is the mean of first data set.

X_2 is the mean of second data set.

S_1^2 is the standard deviation of first data set.

S_2^2 is the standard deviation of second data set.

N_1 is the number of elements in the first data set.

N_2 is the number of elements in the second data set.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Sr. no	Participants (N)	Game	Mean (ACMT)	Standard Deviation
1)	26	Team game	21.44	3.74
2)	26	Individual	17.32	3.30

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Table 2: Independent “t” test on sports achievement motivation level between team game players and individual game players

Group	N	Mean	S.D	“t” value
Team game	26	21.44	3.74	0.0001
Individual	26	17.32	3.30	

Graphical representation of mean values of team game and individual players.

From the present study we have concluded that-

- There is no significant difference found between the team game players and individual players in relation to Sports Achievement Motivation.
- On the basis of mean scores it is found that team game players were having more Sports Achievement Motivation level than individual players.

In player's life coaches and colleagues play an important role. Sports achievement motivation playing most important role. Thus, sports achievement motivation influences other factors affecting performance in sport like physical preparation, technique, tactics and even life style. G. Ponraniet al., (2016) takes the study on determine the differences and level of achievement motivation in State level Football and hockey players and Inter University Badminton and Table tennis players. The study shows that, the level of significance for the study was chosen as 0.05. The results of the study revealed that State Footballers had higher and Inter University table tennis players had lower level of achievement motivation amongst the group Sports achievement motivation cannot be described as something that occurs during competition but mostly as a trait having permanent character being formed during the preceding weeks, months and years. The individual players were need to be motivated. To enhance motivation, the coaches must analyse and respond not only to the player's personality and situational characteristics.

That's why the above study reveals that both game and individual players are mostly similar to each other so there were no significant different found in both games' players and individual players. The present study revealed that the mean value of team players has greater sports achievement motivation in comparison to individual players.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of conclusions drawn, following recommendations was made:

1. Further studies can be done by involving large numbers of samples size.
2. Similar study may be conducted using subjects from different institution for making reliable research,
3. More study may be conducted on different Sex and age group.

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